
An Overview of Naga Languages: Historical Perspective, Features and Challenges

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ABSTRACT

There are 15 recognized Naga tribes in the State of Nagaland in the Northeast of India, with their respective languages, which fall under the Tibeto-Burman group. In the latter part of the 19th Century, preliterate Nagas adopted the Roman script which was introduced to them by the American Missionaries. Subsequently, the German vowel umlaut ü, was incorporated into their alphabet. As there is no common Naga language, there is no common native term for them as a people. UNESCO lists Naga languages under the category of threatened languages of the world. The significance of this study lies in the presentation of the multilingual nature of the Naga community, their shared language features and the differences in the details. The article seeks to give an overview of the same. It will also highlight issues and challenges that Naga languages are faced with. The trajectory of Naga languages from oral to written form will be briefly discussed. Naga languages remain an important and fertile site for research

Introduction

Nagaland is situated in the northeast of India, which got statehood in 1963 as the sixteenth state of India. There are 15 recognized Naga tribes in Nagaland with their own respective languages, namely, Angami, Ao, Chakhesang, Chang, Khiamniungan, Konyak, Lotha, Phom, Pochuri, Rengma, Sangtam, Sümi or Sema, Tikhir, Yimkiung, and Zeliang. Hence, as there is no one common Naga language, there is no common native term for them as a people, and the nomenclature “Naga” is a name given to them by others. The origin of the term is varied. Some say it stems from the meaning of the derivative word which

indicates ‘a young man’; ‘naked’ people etc. (Woodthorpe 47). Due to this complex nature of Naga languages, as with the larger Indian Context, English is the official language of the State. Besides Nagaland State, Nagas inhabit parts of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, and Burma (now Myanmar). There is the popular account of how an Angh’s house falls under India and Myanmar according to the international border demarcation. Tonyei Phawang, the said Konyak Angh of Longwa village, recently remarks, “I eat in Myanmar and sleep in India” (The Times of India).

Ancestral Naga people, who did not have their own script, adopted the Roman script which was introduced by the American Missionaries in the latter part of the 19th Century. Subsequently, the German vowel umlaut ü, as in the German word ‘für’ was incorporated into their alphabet. Naga languages, based on the classification of George Grierson, fall under the Tibeto-Burman sub-family (Hutton). However, Native knowledge about the intricacy of their own languages, with the exception of a few concerned individuals and researchers, do not go much beyond such generalized statements.

There is a dearth of Naga language studies, although in the recent years, research is picking up, especially at Nagaland University. UNESCO report, “Atlas of the World’s Languages in Danger” (2009) lists Naga languages under the category of threatened languages of the world. What is of serious concern, is that the younger generations are fast losing a firm grip over their native languages, as will be seen.

On the whole, Naga languages have many sub-dialects and variants, but the one into which the Bible has been translated, usually acts as the formal common language of a tribe.

Methodology and Significance of the Study

This article is based on a short term project on a study on aspects of Naga Languages, funded by State Council of Educational Research and Training, Nagaland. The study has been mainly conducted through a series of discussions and interaction with individuals manning the Language section of the State of Nagaland. Questionnaires were distributed to Language Officers/Assistant language Officers/Language Assistants attached to the Directorate of School Education. Concerned individuals were approached, and Literature Board Members of some tribes were also consulted.

The significance of the study lies in the presentation of the multilingual nature of the Naga community in the Northeast of India, their common shared features and the differences in the details. There is hardly any collective study of the Naga languages, as such, the article seeks to give an overview of the same. It will also highlight issues and challenges that Naga languages are faced with. The trajectory of Naga

languages, from oral to written form, will be briefly discussed under three sections, namely, Preliterate Ancestral Period, Adoption of Script in the Colonial Period, and Naga Languages in Post Colonial times.

1. Preliterate Ancestral Period (Prior to 1832)

The year 1832 marked the year that the British first set foot in the Naga inhabited regions, which subsequently changed the course of Naga history (Mills). Preliterate times are primordial times of oral traditions, of warrior clansmen, and morungs as informal learning centres with no written script. A popular “Naga story” exists about a lost script which is probably a folktale to explain away the reason why they do not have a script unlike the plainsmen (Hutton 291). It goes, that unlike the plainsmen of Assam whose script was given to them by the Deity on stone/paper, the Naga tribes’ script was written on animal skin which the dog ate. Hutton, however, notes of how sign language was highly efficient among the Nagas, as the necessity of communication between villages speaking different dialects or languages, existed. Oral narratives such as folktales, folksongs, folk sayings and oral accounts, served to record their history. Religious beliefs, customary laws, and taboos regulated their lives. Naga villages functioned independently, guided by a group of elders with *khel*/Clan representations. Some tribes have a village chief like the *Sümi*, or a king-like *Angh*, as with a certain section of the Konyaks. However, in general, the Nagas have a democratic nature of village polity and governance. In fact, the Angami natives were seen as practising a kind of “purest democracy” (Hutton 143). That each tribe, even village, enjoys a certain independence having an insular existence, is reflected by the numerous dialects of a single tribe. In some cases there are almost as many dialects as there are villages of a single tribe. For instance, Angami villages like, Kohima, Khonoma, Jotsoma, Mezoma, Tuophema, Meriema etc., have variations of the same language. Some tribes have varieties of speech forms. The Ao tribe, for instance, have three varieties of Chungli, Mongsen, and Changki, which are vastly different from each other.

2. Adoption of Roman Script in the Colonial Period (1832 to 1947)

With the coming of American missionaries, natives began to read and write in Roman script with the added German letter *ii* which has proved to represent a crucial speech sound for Naga tribes. With the presence of many dialects and speech forms in a single tribe, standard language for a tribe came into use. The dialect accepted to be the common language for a tribe is generally the dialect which is used by the missionaries to read and write, one which is used for the translation of the Bible.

With the set up of formal educational institutions, of mission schools and Government schools, the morungs which functioned as the informal learning institutions, slowly became non-functional. The first schools were mission schools, followed by government schools. The first school was established in 1878 at Molungyimsen by American Baptist missionaries under W.E. Clark. The oldest surviving school is the Clark Memorial Higher Secondary School at Impur, which celebrated its 125th anniversary in 2020 (Morung Express).

Ethnographers, Imperial officials, researchers such as McCabe, Sir George Grierson, Hutton, J.P. Mills, C. von Fürer-Haimendorf, Mary Clark were some notable early recorders of the Naga people and their languages.

3. Naga Languages in Post Colonial times (1947 onwards)

With the departure of the British, Naga political struggle for independence intensified. In 1963, Nagaland State became the sixteenth State of the Union of India. In the absence of a common native language, English was formally adopted as the official language for the state of Nagaland.

In keeping with the Indian policy of 3-Language Formula set in motion by the 1968 National Policy Resolution, native languages of the respective districts are taught in schools, but in the urban areas of highly mixed populations, schools are unable to cater to different native language speakers, leading to poor native language skills of students in these urban areas.

Expansion of educational institutions across the State made much progress. Nagaland University was established in 1994, through an Act of Parliament, Act No. 35 of 1989, and North Eastern Hills University Campuses at Kohima and Medziphema came within its fold. For the first and only time, a Naga language, Tenyidie, was introduced as a Department in Nagaland University in 1997. Today, the University department is running MA and PhD programmes, besides offering certificate and diploma courses. It must be noted, here, that the tribal name “Tenyimia” is a larger inclusive name, of which Angami tribe is a part of the group. It follows that all members of Angami tribe are Tenyimia people, the descendants of their ancestral father, Tenyiu, but not all Tenyimia people are Angami people. The common language of the people is called Tenyidie. Angami and Tenyidie can be interchangeably used.

Features of Naga Languages

- The complex nature of Naga tribes and their dialects have been pointed out. Under a single tribe, there can be dialect variations according to villages. There is also the issue of the language of a tribe having varieties, where the villages of the same tribe vastly differs from each other that they are unintelligible to each other. Haokip notes that in the northeast, the distinction between language or dialect is elusive, that whether a particular speech form is to be counted as a language or dialect is not determined by the sociolinguistic criterion of mutual intelligibility. Of how two scenarios may arise out of peoples’ attitudes. Thereby, people who speak closely related speech forms and are sometimes mutually intelligible, may profess themselves as speaking different languages being different tribes,

as in the case of the Kuki-Chin languages of Manipur. On the contrary, a group of people who despite speaking mutually unintelligible languages persist in learning at least one of the speech forms, being one tribe, as in the case of the Tangkhuls.

- In fact, such differences of varieties, at times, exist within a single village, as with the Ao tribe where Chungli (now standard language) and Poetic Mongsen which houses the folksongs co-exist side by side, so much so, that within a family it is not strange for them to find husband and wife conversing in each one's own (Temsula Ao).
- Nagas have adopted the Roman alphabets, in general. The Literature Board of Chakhesang (Chokri group) has adopted an extra letter, 'ö', in their script and has 28 letters (26 roman letters+ ü+ ö) which is the highest alphabetical set, while most of the tribes have 27 letters (26 roman letters + ü). Tenyidie teaches 25 (minus q and x + ü).
- Nagas have adopted the usage of German vowel with Umlaut 'ü', which has proved to be very efficient as the letter sound is very conspicuous in the Naga languages. Ü is a sound not present in English (Sprachlingua).
- In the teaching of the alphabets, while a few tribes have adapted a native-friendly approach, many have a mixture of native and English sounds. For instance, alphabets A, B, C, D, in Tenyidie are taught as, A /[^]/ as in cut; B^ü; C^ü as in /f/; D^ü and so on.
- With the exception of Sema/Sümi language, 'q' and 'x' are not normally used. Sümi has many "guttural" sounds in their language and they use these alphabets to represent such words. Mikkel Wilson's "How to Pronounce Uvular/Guttural Sounds" aids in an understanding of such sounds.
- There is a tendency in particular languages where letter pairs 'p,b'; 't,d'; 'k,g'; 'b,v'; 'j,z'; 'r,l' are not differentiated much. For instance, 'p,b'; 't,d'; 'kg' for Ao, Khamniungan natives, 'j,z' for Zeliang natives etc.
- Naga languages are tone languages, and a change of tone or pitch of a word changes its meaning. Seventy percent of languages are said to be tonal (Yip). Literature Board of the Chakhesang (Chokri group) portrays 6 tones, which is the highest number of tones/pitches, followed by Angami/Tenyidie at 5 as projected in their dictionary, *MKS Dieda*. It may be noted, that there are others who project Tenyidie to have 4 tones, as pointed out by Meyase in his article, "Four versus Five: The Number of Tones in Tenyidie". Some Literature Boards have presented the tones in their school textbooks, the rest are yet to do so. It follows from this, that the study of tones is tentative and debates go on, though it gives a fair picture of the same. The most common is the 3-tone set.

- Unlike English, and somewhat like Spanish which is a “phonetic language”, Naga words are consistently pronounced as they are spelt and letters are pronounced in the same way except for changes in tones (BBC Bitesize). However, tones may differ for similar words and sometimes to avoid confusion, certain tones are marked. With Sümi, at writer’s own discretion, sometimes a preceding consonant is doubled to indicate high tone (Teo). Phom tribe also resort to such ways in order to differentiate the tones (*Phom Nyiangkuk: Spelling in Phom*).
- Common suffixes of most Naga languages indicate gender and number, while a few show otherwise. For instance, Rengma seems to have no suffixes to indicate number, and the word ‘many’ or similar words, accompany the nouns.
- In the case of loan words, borrowed words are often modified to suit native users. For instance, a particular feature of Angami/Tenyidie is that almost all syllables end with a vowel. This is the reason why some loan words or non-native words are modified and pronounced to suit native speakers e.g. Sahib becomes ‘Shaha’, Dal becomes ‘Dali’. Even some proper nouns undergo such changes e.g. Moses becomes ‘Mosa’, Titus becomes ‘Tita’ to suit Tenyidie speakers.
- Compounding or bringing words together to form new words, is found to be a useful way of introducing new words and terms especially in the society’s transition from a simple oral existence to a literate educated community, from a traditional rural communal life to an ever-increasing urban modern way of life.
- The Naga languages are verb-final languages and has an SOV (Subject-Object-Verb) order, while English has an SVO (Subject-Verb-Object) order. Again, while English have prepositions, Naga languages have postpositions. Example:

English	Angami/ Tenyidie
S v o	s o v
I drink milk	A thunudzü krieya
	(I milk drink)
 Preposition	 Postposition
Behind the door	kikhau siekou
	(door the behind)

- A Language is a reservoir of culture and identity of a people. Though Naga people do not have a common native language and their history, as a people, is subjected to speculations, their common

bonds are, everywhere, displayed in the vocabulary and conceptual terms of their respective languages. For instance, they have their respective term for warriors, Agütomi in Sümi; Lakhühongbü in Chang; Naomei in Konyak; Kanghok in Phom; Athrongrü in Sangtam etc. So also they have respective terms for common dormitories or morungs, ritual abstinence from fieldwork, agriculture-related festivals etc.

Challenges

- As discussed, there is no common Naga language which can be a challenging issue. This is also a reason why tribalism exists in the Naga society. To help better communication and understanding, The Kohima Educational Trust, brought out *Key Words: A Glossary of Sixteen Nagaland Languages*, with the belief that better language could be part of the solution (Chasie). Just as the NPSC expects an administrative officer to learn any one other Naga language besides the language of one's own individual tribe, it will go a great mile if other officers and members of the Naga society are duly encouraged to learn one another's language. As of now, some words or terms from particular native tribes have been adopted as common words for the Nagas in general, like *Eno* (Mr), *Enoli* (Mrs), *Eli* (Miss), *Ahza* (law).
- Nagamese can be a controversial issue especially between native literary figures and linguists. The former individuals are wary of Nagamese being not an ancestral language of the Nagas that is seen to have potentials to dilute Naga languages. On the other hand, there are the linguists who would rather look at the benefits for giving access to communication. Nagamese is a pidgin made up of neighbouring Assamese language, Bengali etc., used as the lingua franca commonly used for trading purposes which is considered, more and more, as a creole language.
- What is a serious concern is that the younger generations are fast losing a firm grip over their native languages. Following the 3-language policy of India, their respective mother tongue, Hindi, and English are to be taught in their schools. However, many students in the mixed urban areas of Nagaland, such as in Kohima, the capital, and the commercial hub-bub of Dimapur district, many students never get the opportunity to read and write in their own mother tongue because schools are unable to accommodate the numerous languages in a single class. It can only be hoped that educational institutions engage language teachers as far as possible.
- Today, languages recognized by the State are taught in schools, mostly up to class 8, a few up to class X11, only one language, Ao, at the under-graduate level, and one language, Tenyidie, at the University level. At the time of writing, Lotha language to be introduced as a component at the

Undergraduate level, is underway. Languages of some tribes need adequate text books to upgrade their level of study.

- The literature boards of the respective languages shoulder the challenging task of looking after the welfare and development of the languages. The Language Officers of the State, too, work in close association with the literature boards while preparing school text books. Only about three literature Boards have reflected the number of tones in their languages. There is the need for language teachers to attend relevant trainings, from time to time.
- There is urgent need to collect and document folk narratives. With the passing away of older generations, reservoirs of oral traditions are depleting. Unless documented, considerable folk knowledge will be lost forever. There is the challenge for projects to be undertaken by researchers, tribal hoho/organizations and NGOs.
- Dictionaries, grammar, traditional oral materials continue to be documented. Lack of such standardized materials create major drawbacks.
- Inter-disciplinary, multidisciplinary studies and collaborations, as also inter-national ventures, especially with neighbouring south-east Asian countries which offer vast possible comparative studies, remain a challenge to be undertaken.

Conclusion

Naga people, besides Nagaland State, inhabit parts of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, and Burma (now Myanmar). They do not have a common native language, and the term 'Naga' is given by others for their general appearance. Thus, although they were not intelligible to each other, for a long period of time in history, their general appearance and folklores have commonalities. As discussed, their languages, too, share common features, such as, SOV order in a basic sentence formation, postpositions, as also being tonal languages. However, their languages can differ much in the details, of how Sümi language has distinct uvular and velar sounds which is also called throaty and guttural; how in Tenyidie, almost all syllables have vowel endings and so on.

Because many Northeastern languages are yet to be systematically studied and documented, Ramkumar Mukhopadhyay warns that many languages of the region will wither away if no positive initiative is taken by the native speakers, academic institutions, institutes of languages, state and central academies and the concerned state governments. Naga languages remains an important and fertile site for research. It remains to be acknowledged that down the ages, individuals, both native and non-native, have kept vigil over Naga languages, orally and in print. Much has been done, much more needs to be done.

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